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ADHESIVE TECHNOLOGIES USED IN DENTISTRY.

Abstract.

The introduction of VI generation adhesives marks a significant advancement, allowing for effective bonding to both enamel and dentin through a total bonding method. By offering comparable adhesion strength to traditional acid etching methods while simplifying application, these modern systems promise to improve clinical outcomes and patient satisfaction.

Key words: *Adhesive, chemical composition, physical properties, mechanism of action*

Due to the rapidly changing situation in the dental materials market, as a result of the constant emergence of new adhesive systems, it is important for the practitioner to choose an adhesive that gives reliable and durable results. Bonding systems differ from each other in many respects: chemical composition, physical properties, mechanism of action, etc. Despite this, the doctor at a clinical appointment is faced with a choice of which adhesive system to choose in a particular clinical case. Until recently, the development of dental adhesives was represented by five generations of bonding systems, the difference of which is the method of processing the smear layer. With first generation adhesives, conventional bonding methods were used with less hydrophilic enamel to provide a bond on highly hydrophilic dentin tissue: after etching, a universal adhesive was applied [1]. When using second generation adhesives, an attempt was made to include a smear layer, which was removed in first generation systems. The goal was to infiltrate the blurred layer with monomers and thus stabilize it. Generation III adhesives emerged from the realization that hydrophilic dentin must be transformed into a hydrophobic state to provide a stronger bond with non-polar adhesives. Therefore, the bonding process was divided into the following steps: 1. Etching only the enamel. 2. Treatment of dentin by etching with special conditioners, often containing maleic acid (maleic acid is weaker than phosphoric acid, however, it is capable of dissolving or changing the eroded layer). 3. Infiltration of treated dentin with a primer: hydrophilic monomers that cover the dentin surfaces with their polar groups and ensure the binding of the adhesive component with non-polar groups. 4. Binding of the adhesive component to primer monomers [3, 6]. Generation IV adhesives combine etching of enamel and dentin with phosphoric acid, although they require two sequential etching stages: one for enamel (30 to 60 s), the other for dentin (15 s). V generation adhesives are used when carrying out the full etching method, but at the same time the stages of primer and bonding processing (which were separated in IV generation systems) are combined into one stage (system in one bottle). This combination resulted in a reduction in adhesive strength in laboratory tests of approximately 10-30%! This generation of adhesives can be considered a breakthrough in the development of adhesive systems. Gen-

eration I-IV adhesives provide a certain increase in adhesive strength with each subsequent new generation, while generation V systems focus on combining individual steps, thus facilitating the use of adhesives. Despite the fact that V generation adhesives are very convenient, their use has led to a number of errors and complications. The fact is that it is very difficult for a doctor to determine whether dentin is overdried or, conversely, too wet by eye. If the dentin is too wet, the restoration is not stable (the filling simply falls out). If the dentin is overdried, then a complication such as post-filling sensitivity appears. Some manufacturers began to produce additional bottles with a specially treated liquid that contained water and fluoride and was applied to the dentin before the adhesive immediately after etching. But this negated the advantages of generation V adhesive systems, since an additional step appeared in the work. Of course, this also significantly increased the cost of restoration. In addition, Generation V adhesives could not be used with chemically or dual-cure materials. Manufacturers are faced with a dilemma on how to use the advantages of the V generation and avoid its disadvantages. Modern VI generation adhesive systems are used not only on enamel, but also on dentin (total bonding method). They provide the same adhesive strength to prepared enamel and dentin as bonding materials that require an acid etching method. Typically, composite materials are bonded using a conditioner, primer, and adhesive [2, 4, 5]. • Conditioners (acids) dissolve the enamel and dentin surfaces and thus create microretention.

• Primers prepare conditioned dentin for application of resin-based filling material. • Adhesives actually bond the filling material to the dentin and/or enamel. The adhesives used today form a smooth transition between the adhesive system and the corresponding filling materials. Dentinal adhesion provides additional binding of composite filling materials or binding exclusively to dentin with special adhesives. Dentin is a living organic tissue and, unlike enamel, exhibits different properties when enamel adhesives are used. In addition, when teeth are prepared with dental instruments, a so-called smear layer is formed on the surface of the dentin. It consists of particles of collagen and hydroxyapatite, dissolved dentin and odontoblast, blood residues, saliva and cooling aerosol liquid. The smear layer can penetrate open dentinal tubules to a depth of 2 to 6 μm .

There are three ways to solve the smear layer problem: 1. Impregnation (i.e. preservation) of the smear layer. Now usually not used due to unstable binding. 2. Complete removal of the smear layer by applying a conditioner (acid or complex calcium component), such as phosphoric acid, for 15-20 seconds. The depth of decalcification ranges from 1 to 10 microns (depending on the conditioner). Then, depending on the procedure, the first (primer application) and second (application of the adhesive itself) steps are performed. 3. Dissolution of the smear layer and integration of its components into the adhesive layer. The addition of weak organic acids (eg maleic acid) or acidic monomers provides an etching effect which, depending on the system, also serves to etch the enamel. There is certainly relative versatility in modern adhesives. However, recent research suggests that the use of many adhesive systems has a number of disadvantages (osmotic bubbling, formation of "water trees", emulsion polymerization, etc.). The structure of vital and devital dentin is different, and when working with these two types of dentin, it is necessary to solve different problems [7]. When working on vital dentin, the following requirements are imposed on the adhesive system: • Absence of postoperative sensitivity. • No toxic effect on the dental pulp. • Sufficiently strong adhesion. • Easy to apply. • Possibility of using the adhesive system with both light- and chemical-curing materials. When working on sclerotic dentin (pulpless tooth), other requirements are imposed on the adhesive system: • Uniform and sufficiently deep penetration of the adhesive into the sclerotic dentinal tubules. • Possibility of using the system in root canals. • The system can be used with both light-curing and dual-curing materials. • Possibility of using the system for cementing in-channel structures. It is obvious that in different clinical situations the dentist will need different adhesive systems. Let's look at examples. Clinical case 1 On a vital tooth, fissure caries is diagnosed at the level of average caries or dentin caries. The doctor's task in this situation is rational necrectomy while maximally preserving healthy tooth tissue. The damage to fissures by caries may indicate weak caries resistance of the enamel. In this case, we need to ensure complete protection of the dentin-pulp system. We choose the self-etching adhesive system "Contax" DMG. The maleic acid contained in the primer effectively penetrates into the dentinal tubules, modifying the smear layer of dentin. In addition, the self-etch adhesive creates good conditions for micromechanical adhesion to the enamel. After applying the primer and carefully spreading it over the enamel and dentin, a mixture of bond and activator is prepared. This mixture is applied in an even layer to dentin and enamel. After this, the entire adhesive system is illuminated.

An activator is added to the bond for additional chemical polymerization, but does not eliminate exposure. The chemical component of polymerization is necessary for complete and uniform adhesion both to dentin and enamel, and to filling materials (including chemically cured materials). In this case, it is recommended to perform restoration with a composite. Clinical case 2 It is necessary to restore a previously pulpless tooth. In this case, it is necessary to create a reliable

support for subsequent restoration. Considering that dentin is sclerotic, we chose the Luxa Bond-Total Etch adhesive system. We unseal the canal to half its length. We use a special reamer, which effectively removes gutta-percha and eliminates perforation, then we etch the dentin outside and inside the canal with phosphoric acid for 15 s. After this, we thoroughly rinse and dry the dentin. Pre-Bond is applied to revitalize sclerotic dentin. It is rubbed into the etched surface for 15 seconds using the Endobrush DMG applicator. As a result, the adhesive system is able to penetrate deeper into the dentinal tubules. At the next stage, an adhesive layer is created. Bond A and Bond B are mixed, one drop at a time, the mixture is rubbed into the work surface for 20 s using Endobrush DMG. Polymerization of the bonding system occurs under the influence of chemical factors, which ensures the creation of a complete adhesive layer in the most inaccessible parts of the root canal. Then material is introduced into the canal to fix the LuxaCore Z Dual fiberglass pins. The uniqueness of the material lies in the fact that it can simultaneously be used for fixation of intracanal structures and for restoration of the tooth stump. Thanks to DMG's patented nanotechnology, the zirconium dioxide-based material has remarkable mechanical properties. LuxaCore Z-Dual conforms to natural tooth structure better than any other core restoration material. A "Luxa Post" pin is installed inside the canal. The pin has the same elastic modulus as tooth dentin, so it does not have a negative effect on tooth tissue. The new generation "LuxaPost" pins are silanized at the factory and are radiopaque. This simplifies the work and saves time, since no additional silane treatment is required. The entire system is illuminated after the formation of the tooth stump. All components inside the canal are connected to each other as a result of chemical adhesion, thereby forming a durable and safe monolithic intra-canal stump inlay. Thus, different clinical situations require the use of different adhesive systems.

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